

PROBLEMATIC BEHAVIOR OF STUDENTS WITH AUTISM IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract:

Referring to this study, its purpose is to identify the level of knowledge of parents, citizens and professionals as well as educators regarding the level of recognition of children with autism. Objectives, aims of the work are: to know the level of engagement these classmates (learners) know and analyze the anxiety of young parents and professionals, how much they work with these children, and in this paper, we will analyze the weaknesses in the recognition of working methods with these children and the provision of contemporary methods during the teaching hours. Work analyzes have been done directly with the students in the classroom. Also within the framework of this paper are questionnaires and surveys directly with parents of these children and professionals dealing with this thematic of the problem, analyzed the encyclopedic dictionary research, to know the term autistic. During the study of literature and data processing developed during our research, we have concluded that: knowing autism as a phenomenon, but also as a term that is still widespread, shows that the integration of autistic children into a regular education system is very necessary and needs no education, and their integration into special schools. From the conclusions drawn from this paper, we think that we have to organize many workshops with the children with the parents of these children and with the responsible persons dealing with the education of these children to clarify what is autism and its characteristics, as the paper has concluded that there is a lack of information about these children.

Keywords: autism, education, parents, professionals, educators, awareness, topics

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1. Introduction

1.1 Chronological analysis of the problem of autism in children

The topic of this paper is to identify the level of knowledge of pupils in learning and the level of readiness of their mothers as well as educators regarding autism, difficulties of working with autistic children and their integration / incitement methods in society, concretely in the regular classes for their inclusion in the teaching. The different types of learning difficulties and their degree of development significantly affect the inclusion and integration of students into interactive learning activities. Studying learning difficulties is of particular importance in the cognitive and methodological viewpoint in order to design teaching strategies, treatment of learning disabilities, and inclusion of all students in learning activities. From a social point of view, the study will highlight the importance of respecting human rights in the field of education in order to benefit from equal opportunities for all. The process of student engagement with NVE is a not only accepted reality but also a concrete activity in our schools. The main factors interacting with the school institution, both inside and outside the school, teachers, students, parents, knowledge, skills and attitudes will enable the success of this process. (M. Ekipson, G.H.2016)

The process of stress and the manifestation of their effective behaviors whenever they need to be engaged in performing classroom tasks, their involvement in specific educational processes.

Poor communication and low socialization of autistic children may present obstacles and need for additional work with these children as well as for educators and their teachers

Each of the teachers should know the nature of this syndrome and the methods they should use in their daily work with them, in order to provide you with the most appropriate care and support at their level of education and especially at the level of their involvement in learning, especially with particular emphasis on the aspect of their socialization. (J. Ericson, 2014)

Societies are distinguished from each other primarily by the way they raise, educate and care for all children without exception. In global society, a billion people live with a disability, involving almost 15% of the world's population. Of these 93 million are children with moderate to severe disabilities; they are 1 out of 20 children aged 0-14. In some countries, having an inability doubles the chances of a child to abandon school the rights of millions of children with disabilities have not yet been realized; It is vital that states provide the conditions for the realization of the right to a quality and equal education. (E. Duela T., 2014.)

Apart from the stress and the phobia of interventions and poor communication, these children also need special diet and a style of life adapted to their needs, so the recognition by professionals of this syndrome would also help in their work of them with them.

Even the children, but also the parents, as well as the society, the pupils, the district, the social environment in which they live and work, must be made clear that society will accept these children in the best possible way. Also, parents and teachers should be encouraged to work hard with this kid. (D. Bardha, 2014)

1.2 The analysis, the purposes of the research (research) are:

1. Provide a more accurate and clear analysis of the recognition of autism by parents, especially parents with their first children;
2. Also analyze which of the methods used in teaching these children brings productivity and results to work;
3. To explore and highlight what are the weaknesses in recognizing working methods with these children, in schools and in pre-school institutions;
4. Provide a clearer analysis in terms of working curriculum with these children, and in the curriculum design and work program in schools. (D. Bardha, 2014)

Parents' right to choose the kind of education they find best for their children, even special education. 4-What are the problems that children with special needs may face and not, as well as teachers in inclusive classes?

According to studies of recent decades, the benefits in the academic and social field are low or moderate. Although the positive developmental and behavioral effects of children with NVE are noticed, they are still less integrated in society, less accepted, have less social skills, and higher levels of problem behaviors. (Greshman & Mac Millan 1997)

Research needs to continue to assess new situations, other people, new opportunities, mutual admirers, long-term solutions, more successful results,

"Relationships between degrees and types of learning difficulties and the level of student acceptance in the normal classes. • Relationship between students' academic, emotional, social performance and demographic characteristics (age, gender, place of residence); • Attitude to EGJ evidencing the acceptance or rejection of NNVE in normal classes; • Teachers' attitudes towards school policy, practice and culture aimed at the acceptance of NNVE and coordinated parent-teacher support; • NNVE parents' attitudes to school policy, the forms, achievements, methods of admission, interaction, and teaching at school. "

(D. Bardha, 2014)

1.3 Strategy for recognizing the problematic behavior of students with autism in the classroom

Autistic children may exhibit some unusual and challenging behaviors, in the face of which the method used and planned within the curriculum and the curriculum; do not produce positive results in the class with these autistic children.

In the manual section where we have dealt with the behavioral behavior of children with intellectual disabilities, we have dealt with the methods and techniques necessary to manage the difficult and challenging behaviors they exhibit. Many of the suggestions given to them are entirely reasonable.

From this research process, we have outlined the steps to be followed in the process and the identification of these children in the lesson. First, it must be acknowledged that these characteristics of these children, which are distinguished by others, are a natural consequence of disability and not a choice to behave inappropriately.

"Understanding the impact that this disability has on student behavior will help you improve the chances of a learner with autism to learn and behave in the most appropriate way to the environment and the school. Of course, this does not mean that you accept his inappropriate behavior, but keep calm and understand the situation as you try to help him manage himself and build a repertoire of appropriate behaviors for the environment where these children live and educate." ⁱ

(Save the children, 2010)

These children and students have many difficulties in facing stressful situations, so classroom changes, tasks or activities can be difficult to cope with. In this case, educators, teachers should be careful about mindful of these stressful situations, and the manifest of the behaviors of these children in learning. (D. Dardha, 2014)

The first strategy is to prepare these students for these situations, which are manifested by the behavior of the pre-eminent student, to appoint another student to assist them, but at the same time to rely on classroom assignments and activities. (Woolfolk, A. 2011)

"In some cases it is necessary for a student with autism to spend part of the day in more structured and less stressful environments, such as a school library or other similar places, especially in parks and in a clean, uncluttered environment children. One of the most discussed issues is the support of students with autism in their behavior. Numerous studies have focused specifically on the spectrum of their typical behaviors."

(Musai, Bardhyl, 1999)

"We've said before that behavior is a form of communication, and inappropriate behavior by a student who is part of the autism spectrum is often the only way they know to communicate a desire or need. Determining the cause or cause of behavior is a key factor in understanding behavior and what it is trying to communicate. "Finding the cause of behavior can be considered as the first step in designing an appropriate intervention and substitution of inappropriate behavior with another appropriate one. For this reason, autistic students need your help (but not only) to learn the skills that will help them reduce stress, irritation, improve communication skills, and develop new, better behaviors."

(Turku, A., Sejko, Elbasan, 2002)

2.1.1 Early intervention

"Some of the most successful programs aimed at improving educational opportunities are based on well-planned interventions early in the life of the child. These interventions are carefully designed to improve communication, social interaction, and reduce stress. Even in school, these will be the main goals for this child."

Ballhysa, N., & Kospiri, B. (2009)

2.1.2 Promotion (motivation of a child with autism)

"All of the following strategies and ideas serve the one that should be considered and the long-term objective of our work as a teacher and school and other services in general, which is: to encourage and support the independence of these students." To achieve this goal, it is necessary to develop strategies that are based on a good knowledge of the hardships and strengths of the child with autism in all areas, such as language, social and cognitive. Of course, this requires a lot of creativity, knowledge and flatteriness on your part. (Musai, Bardhyl, 1999.P/Education)

2.1.3. Strategy to help the teacher

"Here, we will give you some guidelines on how to communicate with these students and various strategies you can use to help autistic students develop skills and learn. They can be selected and adjusted according to the age and ability of the students in your class. Communicate more effectively."

2.1.4. Adapting the child to the environment

Rules are an important element in schools and inclusive classes. School rules may be unclear and general for autistic students, so they should be clearly described so that

these students know exactly what is expected of them. (Zabeli, Naser, 2010) For this reason, the rules must be understandable and visible (placing them in a bank or other visible place); in the format suitable for these students (photographer or paintings, images, icons etc.);

"Each of the rules should be patterned according to the rules to give these students the opportunity to practice them through role play and while using this time to teach the consequences if they do not follow the rules; Use positive reinforcement when your child follows the rules. It's very important to always consider the role that the environment (not just the fiery context, but also people in it) play in the manifestation of astute behavior."

"Problems can go well or for badly depending on how we managed the previous events. Remember that the teacher does not have the capacity and the ability to change the student's internal situation, so it is important to adjust our behavior as well as to the classroom and school environment."

(Turku, A., Sejko, Elbasan, 2002,f,78)

And do not forget that behavior has a communicative function.

2.1.5. Management of behaviors of autistic students in the teaching of the educators-teachers

"It is important to keep in mind that every student with autism is an individual and the distinctive features of this limited ability will be expressed in different ways in different students. Understanding and supporting not only the difficulties, but also the strengths of each student is essential so that they can express their potential throughout the school years"

- a) *"Be patient. In certain cases, it seems like these students say or does things that threaten your school authority. Try not to see them as personal, but take them quietly". MASHT.2012*
- b) Their difficulties are a consequence of biological changes in those parts of the brain that regulate social behavior and understanding of situations. Take action to plan the ways you are going to leave the class over time, if the learner with autism shows difficulties in regulating behavior.
- c) Avoid direct confrontation with him when angry or upset by not raising or arguing with him. They are susceptible to noise. The raised voice does not help you understand

what it needs. Use a neutral tone of voice, do not shout and do not expect him to understand the expression on your face. (Michael, D, Powers, 2014)

d) Social skills some autistic students like such activities as drama, acting or role playing, which can be used to teach such social skills, such as greeting, speaking, holding order etc.

e) *"Friendship District. The teacher voluntarily selects a number of 5 to 8 pupils that will create a circle of autistic children. By meeting regularly, they can help the child express their feelings to lower the level of anxiety. This can lead to better social integration and better levels of contact with peers."*

f) *"Close associate. Finding a close relative, mostly of the same age and class, can help this child increase self-confidence. He will have someone to go to if there are difficulties different social."*

g) Mentor. Older children can benefit if they have a mentor who can be a senior student or teacher or part of a school staffer. Children with autism as well as all other disabled children are often victims of bullying (mockery and bullying by friends, *"which occurs repeatedly and goes to the threat of a child's fatal injury*). Try to be attentive to this phenomenon and to take measures to avoid it." (Z. Naser, 1010)

h) Confronting Transition Time. For some autism children such times, such as breaks between hours or large breaks, are difficult because they are unclear and loud. It is important to have alternatives to manage such moments to overcome these problems.

i) *"A Quiet Place. It's important to arrange a place for autistic children in advance, where they can go when they are in anxiety, when they are angry or there is no other person (associate, mentor or friend) that can help.*

j) *Support Team. Most schools have a support team (psychologist, social worker). They can help you with specific counseling and training for certain children. Do not hesitate to ask for their help. Deborah Fein, Michael Dun, 2010"*

k) Close co-operation with parents. Regular contact with the child's family with autism will have mutual benefits. Of course, parents want the best for the child but school staff can provide you with different perspectives.

2.1.6. Teaching Strategy Mechanism with Autistic Children

"Using visual aids. Children with autism make it easier to understand the message through the toolbox. For example, you can use a schedule that tells them time through simple drawings so that they know exactly what to do and when. Many schools in different countries also use computer software to help them. Use lists, artifacts, calendars, photos, etc, that can help you understand the steps you need to follow and predict what will happen next. Photo Swapping System (PECS). It is one of the systems used to teach children with autism, who have considerable delays in language development. Teachers

use photo shoots of this program to teach students with autism the names of different objects."

(Gardner, H. 2002)

"Social stories. Autistic students who are able to read can be taught how to cope with different situations through the technique of social stories. The stories are written by the teacher himself, keeping in mind the child, where he is told by words and simple images, step by step, what will happen in anxiety situations and how to deal with difficult situations (for example a social situation can be used to learn what to do in the street, at bus, friends, etc.)"

(Children, S. t., 2010)

"TEACCH (treatment and education of children with autism and similar communication barriers). This is one of the most implemented models in special schools, but is recently adapting to success in mainstream schools. It is based on changing the environment and the use of visual aids, such as timetables, photos, to help the child have a structured routine. "This routine reduces stress by making it clear what needs to happen during the day, and improves understanding. Children are provided guidance for each stage of activity mainly in visual mode. SPELL (Structure, Positive, Empathy, Low Incentive, and relationship). This model recognizes the individual needs of the individual and emphasizes that all planning and intervention is organized on this basis. Adjust language to student level."

(Children, S. t., 2010)

"Talk slowly and give a few seconds to process new information, then replicate it, or repeat the application once more. Verify if he understands what he should do in the classroom or what tasks he has. The fact that you repeat the instruction you gave does not mean that you understand it. ` The processing of verbal information is difficult, so visual tools can help. Make sure you understand what is expected of him in school, for example where he should be in class or every class, where he should go during the break, etc."

(Lynn Brenan nga USA, 2014)

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